

OPERATIONS AND MAINTENANCE MANUAL

Stormwater Drainage Facilities

HANSON HOMES RESIDENCE LOT 1 – KINGS

583 S Webb Avenue, East Wenatchee, WA 98802
Parcel No.: 22211430018 | Kings Short Plat Lot 1, Douglas County, WA

PROJECT INFORMATION	
Prepared For:	Hanson Homes Construction LLC
Address:	630 Valley Mall Parkway, East Wenatchee, WA 98802
Prepared By:	Arlen Brazill, Engineering Design Technician
Engineer of Record:	Justin Wilson, P.E., Complete Design Inc.
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1. Purpose and Applicability

This Operations and Maintenance (O&M) Manual has been prepared pursuant to the requirements of the 2024 Department of Ecology (DOE) Stormwater Management Manual for Eastern Washington (SWMMEW) and the Douglas County Storm Drainage Ordinance. It establishes the ongoing inspection, maintenance, and record-keeping obligations for the stormwater drainage facilities constructed as part of the Hanson Homes Residence Lot 1 – Kings development located at 583 S Webb Avenue, East Wenatchee, WA 98802.

This manual shall be retained by the property owner, filed with the County, and transferred to any subsequent property owner at the time of sale. The facilities described herein are privately owned and are the sole maintenance responsibility of the current property owner.

IMPORTANT: Failure to perform required maintenance may result in facility failure, property damage, and potential regulatory non-compliance under Douglas County Code and DOE SWMMEW requirements.

2. Stormwater Facility Description

The stormwater management system for Lot 1 of the Kings Short Plat employs a dual Best Management Practice (BMP) approach, each tailored to the specific runoff source it serves. Both BMPs take advantage of the site's native Cashmere fine sandy loam soils (NRCS Hydrologic Soil Group A), which exhibit excellent infiltration capacity.

2.1 BMP T5.10B — Downspout Infiltration/Dispersion (Roof Areas)

Roof stormwater from both the single-family residence and the detached shop is managed using BMP T5.10B — Downspout Infiltration/Dispersion. Gutters collect roof drainage and convey it via 4-inch downspout leaders to grade-level splashblocks at each downspout outlet. Splashblocks disperse roof runoff as sheet flow across adjacent landscaped or open ground, promoting infiltration into the native soils. Splashblocks positioned near the driveway edge direct a portion of roof runoff onto the paved driveway surface for collection by the driveway catch basin.

BMP Designation:	T5.10B — Downspout Infiltration / Dispersion
Drainage Area Served:	Residence roof and detached shop roof
Conveyance:	Gutters, 4-inch downspout leaders
Dispersion Method:	Grade-level splashblocks, sheet-flow dispersion
Receiving Soil:	Cashmere fine sandy loam (HSG A, Ksat 2.0–6.0 in/hr)
Number of Splashblocks:	One per downspout outlet (quantity per final construction drawings)

2.2 BMP F6.22 — Underground Infiltration Trench (Driveway)

Paved driveway and parking area runoff — including splashblock contributions deposited onto the paved surface — is collected by a catch basin fitted with a downturned tee fitting for pre-treatment settling. A 6-inch PVC conveyance pipe directs settled stormwater into the underground infiltration trench. The trench consists of an 8-inch perforated distribution pipe embedded in open-graded aggregate, wrapped in geotextile filter

fabric. Runoff is temporarily stored within the void space of the aggregate and is gradually exfiltrated into the surrounding native soils.

BMP Designation:	F6.22 — Underground Infiltration Trench
Trench Dimensions:	15 ft wide × 32 ft long × 4 ft deep
Tributary Area:	8,382 sf (0.192 ac)
Peak Inflow (100-yr):	0.48 cfs
Volume Provided:	558 cf (at 30% void ratio)
Peak Storage Elevation:	3.88 ft (within 4 ft depth)
Design Exfiltration Rate:	3.6 in/hr (conservative, 0.90 factor applied)
Pre-Treatment:	Catch basin with downturned tee for sediment settling
Conveyance:	6-inch PVC pipe stubbing ~2 ft into trench; 8-inch perforated distribution pipe
Aggregate:	Open-graded, clean crushed rock; wrapped in geotextile filter fabric
Design Storm:	100-year, 24-hour, 2.50 inches (SCS Type II)
Drawdown Time:	59.6 minutes plug-flow detention; well within 72-hour maximum

3. Owner Responsibilities

The property owner of Tax Parcel No. 22211430018 is responsible for:

- Performing all routine and corrective maintenance tasks described in this manual.
- Conducting annual inspections, or more frequently after major storm events.
- Maintaining a completed Stormwater Maintenance Log (Appendix B) for a minimum of five (5) years, and making records available to Douglas County upon request.
- Ensuring that no modifications are made to the stormwater facilities without prior approval from Douglas County and, where required, a licensed engineer.
- Transferring this manual and all maintenance records to any subsequent property owner at closing.
- Notifying Douglas County of any facility failure or observed deficiency that cannot be corrected through routine maintenance within a reasonable timeframe.

4. Prohibited Activities

The following activities are strictly prohibited and may result in facility failure, regulatory penalties, or both:

- Discharging sanitary sewage, gray water, oil, fuel, chemicals, paint, solvents, or other pollutants to any stormwater facility.
- Applying fertilizers, herbicides, or pesticides within 15 feet of any infiltration facility.
- Altering, blocking, filling, or paving over any infiltration facility, splashblock dispersion area, or drainage swale.

- Directing roof, driveway, or other drainage away from the designated stormwater facilities without engineering review.
- Washing vehicles, equipment, or machinery over or near the infiltration trench or splashblock areas.
- Storing materials, equipment, or vehicles on or over the infiltration trench.
- Using chemical deicing agents on the driveway; mechanical snow removal only.

5. Maintenance Procedures — BMP T5.10B Downspout Infiltration/Dispersion

5.1 Gutters and Downspout Leaders

Gutters and downspout leaders convey roof runoff to splashblocks. Blockages will cause overflow, bypassing the intended dispersion system.

Routine Maintenance Tasks:

- Inspect and clean gutters and downspouts at least twice per year: once in spring and once in fall after leaf drop.
- Remove leaves, debris, bird nests, and accumulated sediment from gutters.
- Flush downspout leaders with a garden hose to confirm unobstructed flow from gutter to splashblock.
- Check all gutter hangers and downspout brackets; re-secure any loose fasteners.
- Repair or replace cracked, broken, or disconnected gutter or downspout sections promptly.

Corrective Maintenance Triggers:

- Overflow or bypass of water around a blocked gutter or downspout.
- Visible cracking, separation, or displacement of any gutter or downspout section.

5.2 Splashblocks

Splashblocks disperse concentrated downspout flow as sheet flow across adjacent pervious surfaces. Proper positioning and undisturbed surrounding ground are essential.

Routine Maintenance Tasks:

- Inspect each splashblock annually and after major storm events (1-inch or greater in 24 hours).
- Confirm splashblocks remain in correct position directly beneath each downspout outlet.
- Verify the dispersion area downslope from each splashblock is vegetated, undisturbed, and free of compaction.
- Remove any sediment accumulation or debris from the splashblock surfaces.
- Re-level or reposition any splashblock that has settled, shifted, or been displaced.
- Maintain vegetative cover within the sheet-flow dispersion zone; re-seed bare areas promptly.

Corrective Maintenance Triggers:

- Splashblock missing, broken, or displaced.
- Concentrated flow or erosion observed in the dispersion zone.
- Dispersion zone shows signs of compaction, bare soil, or channelization.

6. Maintenance Procedures — BMP F6.22 Underground Infiltration Trench

6.1 Catch Basin Pre-Treatment Structure

The catch basin, equipped with a downturned tee inlet fitting, functions as the primary pre-treatment sediment trap. Regular cleanout is essential to protect the infiltration trench from sediment loading.

Routine Maintenance Tasks:

- Inspect the catch basin annually and after storm events producing 0.5 inches of rainfall or greater.
- Remove the catch basin lid/grate; inspect interior walls, invert, and the downturned tee fitting.
- Remove and dispose of all accumulated sediment, debris, oil sheen, and floating materials. Do not flush sediment downstream.
- Inspect the downturned tee fitting for physical integrity; confirm it remains securely in place and the opening faces downward.
- Inspect the 6-inch PVC outlet pipe stub for blockage or displacement; flush with a hose to confirm flow.
- Inspect grate or lid for damage; replace if cracked or broken.
- Confirm the catch basin rim elevation is consistent with surrounding paved surface grade; report significant settlement to an engineer.

Corrective Maintenance Triggers:

- Sediment depth exceeds 25% of sump depth.
- Evidence of oil sheen or pollutant discharge.
- Tee fitting displaced, broken, or missing.
- Outlet pipe blocked or disconnected.
- Catch basin structure showing cracks or structural deterioration.

6.2 Infiltration Trench

The infiltration trench is a subsurface structure and cannot be directly observed during normal operation. Maintenance is primarily performance-based: observed drawdown time and surface ponding are the key indicators of facility health.

Routine Maintenance Tasks — Surface and Overflow:

- Inspect the trench area for surface ponding or saturated soils within 24 hours following a 1-inch or greater rainfall event. Full drawdown should occur within 72 hours per SWMMEW requirements.
- Inspect the trench boundary and surrounding area for signs of subsidence, settlement, or depression of the soil surface; investigate and repair any depressions.
- Maintain the 2-foot minimum vegetative buffer around the trench perimeter; do not park vehicles or place heavy loads over the trench footprint.
- Inspect the conveyance pipe from the catch basin to the trench for blockage; flush annually.

Long-Term Performance Monitoring:

- If the trench fails to fully drain within 72 hours of a significant storm event, have the facility evaluated by a licensed engineer.

- The aggregate may require rehabilitation or replacement if clogging occurs. Signs include persistent ponding, backflow into the catch basin, or daylighting of stored water.
- If rehabilitation is required, the geotextile fabric and top aggregate layer are typically replaced; excavation and disposal of sediment-laden aggregate may be necessary.

Corrective Maintenance Triggers:

- Surface ponding persists beyond 72 hours after a storm event.
- Backflow or surcharging observed in the catch basin.
- Evidence of trench overtopping or surface discharge to adjacent properties.
- Subsidence or rutting observed over the trench footprint.

6.3 Driveway Surface Drainage

The paved driveway is graded at 2% cross-slope to direct runoff to the catch basin. Proper surface grades must be maintained.

- Inspect the driveway surface annually for cracking, heaving, potholes, or grade changes that could redirect flow away from the catch basin.
- Seal-coat or repair asphalt pavement as needed to prevent cracking that could allow infiltration under the pavement near the trench.
- Remove accumulated sand, sediment, or debris from the driveway surface; do not sweep or wash grit and sediment into the catch basin.
- After winter snow removal, inspect the driveway and catch basin area for plowing damage.

7. Inspection Schedule Summary

The following table summarizes minimum inspection frequencies for all stormwater facilities. Additional inspections shall be performed within 48 hours following any storm event producing 1 inch or more of rainfall in a 24-hour period.

Facility / Component	Minimum Frequency	Key Inspection Items
Gutters & Downspouts	2x per year (spring & fall)	Debris, blockages, physical damage, secure attachment
Splashblocks	Annual + post-storm	Position, dispersion zone condition, erosion, vegetation
Catch Basin / Pre-Treatment	Annual + post-storm	Sediment depth, tee fitting integrity, outlet pipe, grate
Infiltration Trench (surface)	Annual + 72-hr post-storm	Drawdown, ponding, subsidence, overland flow
Driveway Surface	Annual	Cracks, potholes, grade integrity, runoff direction
Overall Site	Annual	Erosion, unauthorized fills or paving, vegetation, general drainage patterns

8. Sediment and Waste Disposal

All materials removed from stormwater facilities during maintenance must be handled and disposed of in accordance with applicable local, state, and federal regulations.

- Sediment removed from the catch basin sump shall be disposed of at a permitted solid waste facility. Do not discharge to storm drains, waterways, or pervious areas.
- If oil sheen, fuel odors, or other contaminants are observed during maintenance, the material may require characterization and special disposal. Contact the Washington State Department of Ecology or a licensed waste hauler for guidance.
- Debris removed from gutters and splashblocks may be composted or disposed of in solid waste if non-contaminated.
- Aggregate removed from the infiltration trench shall be inspected for contamination; clean material may be reused or disposed of as inert fill; contaminated material requires special handling.

9. Important Contacts

Engineer of Record:	Justin Wilson, P.E. — Complete Design Inc. 509.662.3699 www.completedesign.cc PO Box 1914, Wenatchee, WA 98807
Douglas County Public Works:	509.745.8527 www.douglascountywa.net
WA Dept. of Ecology (Eastern):	509.329.3400 ecology.wa.gov
WA Dept. of Ecology Spill Line:	1-800-258-5990 (24-hour)
Douglas County Environmental Health:	509.745.8521

10. Conclusion

This Operations and Maintenance Manual establishes the minimum inspection and maintenance requirements necessary to ensure the long-term performance of the stormwater facilities serving the Hanson Homes Residence Lot 1 – Kings development. The dual-BMP system (BMP T5.10B and BMP F6.22) has been designed in full conformance with the 2024 DOE SWMMEW and the Douglas County Storm Drainage Ordinance, and is suited to the excellent infiltration conditions of the native Cashmere fine sandy loam soils on this site.

Consistent execution of the maintenance tasks and inspection protocols described in this manual is essential to protect the facility's design performance over its service life, prevent adverse impacts to adjacent properties and groundwater, and maintain compliance with Douglas County permit conditions.

This manual shall be kept on file at the subject property and be transferred with the property deed at time of sale.

APPENDIX A — Annual Inspection Checklist

Hanson Homes Residence Lot 1 – Kings | 583 S Webb Ave, East Wenatchee, WA 98802 | Parcel No.: 22211430018

Inspection Date: _____	Inspector Name: _____	Weather Conditions: _____	Next Scheduled Inspection: _____
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Facility / BMP	Inspection Item	Acceptable Criteria	Corrective Action if Failed	Pass <input type="checkbox"/>	Fail <input type="checkbox"/>
Gutters & Downspouts	Gutter debris / blockage	Gutters clear; no overflow observed	Clean gutters; remove debris	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Gutters & Downspouts	Downspout free flow	Water flows freely from gutter to splashblock	Flush with hose; clear obstruction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Gutters & Downspouts	Physical damage / loose hangers	No cracked, separated, or loose sections	Re-fasten or replace damaged sections	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Splashblocks	Position at downspout outlet	Splashblock directly under each downspout outlet	Reposition or replace splashblock	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Splashblocks	Dispersion zone vegetation	Vegetated, undisturbed, no bare soil or channelization	Re-seed; remove compaction; redirect flow	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Splashblocks	Erosion / concentrated flow	No rilling or erosion in dispersion zone	Install erosion controls; regrade if needed	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Catch Basin	Sediment depth	Sediment depth < 25% of sump depth	Vacuum or hand-remove sediment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Catch Basin	Downturned tee fitting	Tee fitting in place, opening facing downward, no damage	Re-secure or replace tee fitting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Catch Basin	Outlet pipe (6-in PVC)	Pipe clear; no blockage or displacement	Flush pipe; inspect for damage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Catch Basin	Lid / grate condition	Lid secure; grate intact; no cracking	Replace lid or grate if damaged	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Catch Basin	Oil sheen or pollutants	No oil, fuel, or chemical sheen observed	Contain; contact Ecology Spill Line: 1-800-258-5990	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Infiltration Trench	Surface ponding within 72 hrs	No ponding 72 hours after storm event	Investigate; consult engineer if persistent	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Infiltration Trench	Surface subsidence / settlement	No depression or rutting over trench footprint	Consult engineer; repair as directed	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Infiltration Trench	Overland flow to adjacent property	No overflow or discharge leaving site	Consult engineer immediately	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Infiltration Trench	Conveyance pipe clear	Flow from catch basin to trench unobstructed	Flush or snake conveyance pipe	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Driveway Surface	Pavement cracks / potholes	Surface intact; no large cracks or heaving	Patch or seal coat as needed	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Driveway Surface	Cross-slope / runoff direction	Runoff directed toward catch basin	Regrade or patch to restore 2% cross-slope	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Facility / BMP	Inspection Item	Acceptable Criteria	Corrective Action if Failed	Pass <input type="checkbox"/>	Fail <input type="checkbox"/>
Overall Site	Unauthorized fill or paving over facilities	No fill, paving, or permanent storage over BMPs	Remove immediately; consult engineer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall Site	Vegetative stabilization	All disturbed areas stabilized with vegetation or rock	Re-seed or re-rock bare areas	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Notes / Corrective Actions Taken:	
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